

Investigation of Physico-chemical Attributes and Eutrophication Status of Shahpura Lake, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

Roma Silawat

Research Scholar (Ph.D.), Department of Zoology, Govt. Motilal Vigyan Mahavidhyalaya Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT:

"Bhopal" the capital of Madhya Pradesh also called as the "City of Lakes". One of the lake in Bhopal is the beautiful Shahpura Lake which is suffering from alarming contamination by heavy metal discharge without adequate treatment of pollutants to remove deleterious compounds. This condition is affecting not only to the individual species and population but also to natural ecosystem. The present investigation highlights the Water Quality Index (WQI) of Shahpura Lake water by using physico-chemical parameters like pH, Temperature, DO, BOD, Chloride, Alkalinity, Hardness, Conductivity, Total Dissolved Solids, Chloride, Iron and Turbidity. The present investigation reveals that Shahpura Lake need some acceptable water treatment before its consumption by local population.

KEYWORDS: Contamination, Discharge, Treatment, WQI, Pollutants.

INTRODUCTION:

Water is one of the most believable and vital wealth on our planet Earth [1-6]. Globally, there is expanding awareness that the water will be one of the most censorious natural resource in near future. Water paucity is increasing worldwide. Pressure on existing water sources is increasing because of growing demands in agriculture, domestic, hydropower projects, industries etc. The assessment of water quality is important research topic [7]. Lakes are one of the pertinent water resources used for drinking, irrigation, fisheries and flood control prospective [8-10].

The Shahpura Lake is located near Manisha market of Bhopal. The lake is surrounded by schools, hospitals and human settlements living around the lake area. The lake manifests the marshy vegetation growing at the bank of the lake along with pools and drains which results in enhancement of pollution cost by industrial waste and municipality. Organic waste from neighboring urban sewage, livestock, industrial and hospitality waste accounts

huge contamination. The lake water is also invaded with water hyacinth which regulate the quality of water and provide marked support to bacterial density which in-turn bestow importantly to its growth and nutrient dynamics. The Shahpura Lake pollution is a matter of great concern. Since it has reached flustering level owing to inflow of large amount of raw sewage from its heavily polluted settlements. The lake is eutrophic Lake, the quantity of nutrient is very high and O₂depletion is notable [11].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Shahpura Lake is one of the significant lakes of Bhopal. The lake is situated near Manisha market and Bansal hospital. It covers an average area of 8.29 km². The chief use of lake is for sewage disposal of residential area, irrigation, recreation and aquaculture. The capacity of storage of Lake is 2.29 Mm³ and maximum depth is 5.6 m and minimum depth is 1.5 m. Its coordinates are 23°12'17" N and 77°25'35" E.

Samples	Location	Latitudes	Longitudes
S1	Bansal Hospital	23°12'25" N	77°25'30" E
S2	Near Mamta Marriage Garden	23°12'17.65"N	77°25'3.9"E
S3	Near windsor Temple	23.2110° N	77.4207° E
S4	Near Chitransh Nursery	23°12'27.05"N	77°25'27.71"E
S5	Manisha Market	23.2012° N	77.4252° E

Water samples collected from five different sampling stations. Samples are collected in the month of January 2020. Sterilized bottles are used for collection of samples and analyze by using standard methods of APHA (American Public Health Association). The assessment of various physico-chemical parameters like pH, Temperature, Chloride, Alkalinity, DO, BOD, TDS Fluoride, Turbidity, Iron and Conductivity are carried out. All the reagents and chemicals used in the present study were of analytical grade.

Table: Analysis of Physico-chemical parameters of Shahpura Lake in the month of January 2020

S.no.	Parameters	Unit	Site I	Site II	Site III	Site IV	Site V	WQI Standard Permissible Value (SI)
1	Temperature	°C	21.9	21.9	21.9	21.9	21.9	-
2	pH	-	7.6	7.5	7.5	7.6	7.7	8.5
3	Turbidity	NTU	55	53	54	54	56	5
4	Alkalinity	mg/L	381	380	382	381	381	200
5	Hardness	mg/L	241	240	241	242	242	300
6	Conductivity	mg/L	1157	1155	1154	1155	1156	300
7	TDS	mg/L	579	581	578	576	579	500
8	Chloride	mg/L	74	76	75	74	74	250
9	Fluoride	mg/L	0.8	0.79	0.79	0.8	0.81	1
10	Iron	mg/L	0.37	0.35	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.3
11	DO	mg/L	5.4	5.3	5.5	5.3	5.3	5
12	BOD	mg/L	105	106	106	104	105	6

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Temperature: It is a physical property expressing hotness and coldness of water. It is a significant factor. Besides to its non-effectiveness, it influences several other parameters and can change the physical and chemical properties of water. The mean temperature range of Shahpura Lake is 21.9 °C.

pH: Hydrogen ion concentration is a measure of how acidic and basic water is. The pH scale ranges from 0-14, 7 being neutral, pH less than 7 shows acidity and pH more than 7 shows basicity. The pH value range from minimum to maximum of Shahpura Lake is 7.5 – 7.7.

Turbidity: Turbidity is the cloudiness of water caused by suspended solids that are usually invisible to the naked eye. The value of turbidity range from minimum to maximum of Shahpura Lake is 53 -56 mg/L.

Alkalinity: It is a measure of capacity of water to neutralize acids. The bicarbonate ion is usually common. In the present work the value of alkalinity range from minimum to maximum of Shahpura Lake is 380 – 382 mg/L.

Hardness: The two most common minerals that makes water hard are calcium and magnesium. The value of hardness from minimum to maximum of Shahpura Lake is 240 – 242 mg/L.

Conductivity: It is used to measure the concentration of dissolved solids which have been ionized in water (Polarsolution). The value of conductivity from minimum to maximum in the present work of Shahpura Lake is 1154 – 1157 mg/L.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS): It comprises inorganic salts (chiefly calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium, bicarbonate, chlorides and sulphates) and some small amount of organic matter dissolved. The value of TDS from minimum to maximum of Shahpura Lake is 576 – 581 mg/L.

Chloride: All-natural water contains chloride but mostly the concentration is low. Chloride concentration are lower than those of the sulfates and bicarbonates in the most surfaces streams. The value of chloride from minimum to maximum in the Shahpura Lake is 74 – 76 mg/L.

Fluoride: It is the simplest anion of fluorine. Fluoride's mineral and salts are important chemical reagents. Fluoride gives a distinctive bitter taste. When it's limits exceeds causes Fluorosis. The value of fluoride range from minimum to maximum in Shahpur lake is 0.79 – 0.81 mg/L.

Iron: In the present research work the value of iron was noticed from minimum to maximum is 0.35 – 0.37 mg/L.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO): DO concentration are continuously affected by aeration, diffusion, photosynthesis, respiration and decomposition. The value of DO from minimum to maximum in Shahpura Lake is 5.3 – 5.5 mg/L.

Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD): The amount of dissolved oxygen needed by aerobic biological organisms to break down organic material present in a given water sample at certain temperature over a specific period of time called Biochemical Oxygen Demand. The value of BOD from minimum to maximum in Shahpur lake is 104 – 106 mg/L.

REFERENCES:

- [1] **Anita. and Salahuddin. (2019).** Analysis of Electrical conductivity of Ground water at different locations of Phooli of U.P, India. *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Development*, 3, 1-5.
- [2] **Ansari, Farid. and Salahuddin. (2013).** Groundwater Temperature Variation Analysis of Industrial Area Nandganj, Ghazipur (India). *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7 (14),539-542.
- [3] **Chaudhary, M. P. and Salahuddin (2014).** Analysis of COD in water at different locations of upper lake in Madhya Pradesh. *European Journal of Applied Engineering and Scientific Research*, 3(2), 37-39.
- [4] **Chaudhary, M. P. and Salahuddin. (2015).** Physico-Chemical analysis in winter season of Bhojtal water in Bhopal region of Madhya Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*, 6 (4),78-81.
- [5] **Salahuddin. (2013).** Analysis of Chloride Content in the Surface of water at different locations of Madhya Pradesh. *International Journal for Pharma-ceutical Research Scholars*, 2(4), 107-109.
- [6] **Salahuddin. (2014).** Physico-chemical analysis of upper lake water in Bhopal region of Madhya Pradesh, India. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 5(5), 165-169.
- [7] **Dixit, D, D.C. Rahi (2017).** Physico-Chemical Properties and Eutrophication Status of Shahpura Lake, Bhopal. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Development*, Vol 4, Issue 11, 2017/ISSN: 2321-0613.
- [8] **Chaudhary, M. P. and Salahuddin. (2015).** Physico-Chemical analysis in winter season of Bhojtal water in Bhopal region of Madhya Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*, 6 (4),78-81.
- [9] **Salahuddin. and Husain, Intazar.(2020).** Analysis of Lower Lake Water in Bhopal Region of Madhya Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Lakes and Rivers*.13(1), 17-25.
- [10] **Salahuddin (2021).** Investigation of the Quality of Shahpura lake Water, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India. *SPC Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 3(1) (2021) 10-13.
- [11] **Dixit, D, D.C. Rahi (2017).** Physico-Chemical Properties and Eutrophication Status of Shahpura Lake, Bhopal. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Development*, Vol 4, Issue 11, 2017/ISSN: 2321-0613.